

What should we know about micropollutants removal to apply the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive?

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Abstract

The revised Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD) imposes strict requirements for the removal of micropollutants in urban wastewater treatment plants. Our goal is to provide a comprehensive framework about occurrence, removal efficiency, considering the integration of biological processes and quaternary treatments, and the associated costs related to 12 target micropollutants. The analysis is based on current knowledge from monitored WWTPs available in literature. Additionally, the environmental residual risk has been estimated. This review offers valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities associated with implementing quaternary treatment processes to comply with the UWWTD.

Keywords (maximum 6 in alphabetical order)

Activated carbon adsorption; biological treatment; economic analysis; environmental risk assessment; ozonation; pharmaceuticals

INTRODUCTION

The European Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD) mandates quaternary treatments by 2045 to achieve 80% reduction of micropollutants in wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) of 150,000 population equivalent (PE) or more (European Council, 2024). The UWWTD addresses 12 target micropollutants, grouped in two categories. Category 1 includes 8 pharmaceuticals indicated as “very easy to treat”: Amisulpride (AMS), Carbamazepine (CBZ), Clarithromycin (CLR), Citalopram (CTL), Diclofenac (DCF), Hydrochlorothiazide (HDC), Metoprolol (MTP) and Venlafaxine (VEN). Category 2 includes 4 compounds described as “substances that can be easily disposed of”: Candesartan (CND), Benzotriazole (BTR), Mixture of 4-Methylbenzotriazole (4MBT) and 5-Methylbenzotriazole (5MBT), and Irbesartan (IRB). The compliance with the 80% removal target is verified on the annual average removal of the mix of at least 6 micropollutants: 4 from Category 1 and 2 from Category 2. Biological processes could be not fully effective to achieve this target, depending on micropollutants influent concentrations and biodegradability, and quaternary treatments could be required: processes such as adsorption on activated carbon and ozonation are currently recommended (Bourgin et al., 2018).

This study aims to provide a comprehensive framework about the 12 target micropollutants occurrence in untreated wastewater, their removal efficiency achievable by both biological process and quaternary treatments (ozonation, adsorption on both granular and powdered activated carbon), and costs of quaternary treatments. In addition, residual environmental risk has been estimated to assess the actual level of aquatic ecosystem protection resulting from the enforcing of the UWWTD.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Literature review

For each of the 12 target micropollutant, several parameters were collected to estimate the potential removal efficiency of the biological conventional activated sludge (CAS) process, ozonation and activated carbon adsorption. As for the CAS process, the values of K_d , K_{bio_aer} and K_{bio_anox} parameters were collected; when multiple values for the same micropollutant were available, the median value was used. As for quaternary treatments, parameters related to the reactivity with ozone (K_{O_3} and K_{OH})

and adsorption (K_{OW} and pK_a) were collected: given the limited K_{OH} values available for the target micropollutants, the analysis focused only on K_{O3} .

The concentrations values of the 12 target micropollutants were retrieved from literature, starting from 2010 and selecting only articles (i) describing full-scale WWTPs monitoring, and (ii) reporting data at the WWTPs inlet and/or both at the inlet and outlet of quaternary treatments: ozonation (O_3), adsorption on granular activated carbon (GAC) and powder activated carbon (PAC). Micropollutant concentrations at each treatment step were averaged when multiple values were reported.

Economic analysis of quaternary treatments

Both the capital expenditure (CAPEX) and the operational expenditure (OPEX) were estimated. Costs were calculated as a function of WWTP capacity, with an average flow rate computed assuming a water supply of 250 L/PE/day and a coefficient of sewage influx of 0.8. Hydraulic Retention Time (HRT) for the average flow was assumed equal to 30 minutes for ozonation and adsorption on GAC, while 60 minutes for adsorption on PAC. The equivalent annual cost for CAPEX was assessed assuming a write-off time of 20 years with a discount rate of 3%. The assumptions referred to each process are based on indications from industry professionals.

Environmental risk assessment

The residual environmental risk of the effluent after each treatment step was assessed in terms of Risk Quotient (RQ) as follows:

$$RQ_i = \frac{C_{EFF,i}}{PNEC_i}$$

where $C_{EFF,i}$ is the effluent concentration after each treatment step and $PNEC_i$ is the lowest predicted no effect concentration (PNEC) for the micropollutant i . The PNEC value indicates the concentration below which no risk is expected. River dilution was neglected to simulate a worst-case scenario of low receiving water flow.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Suitability maps for CAS process and the selected quaternary treatments have been built and shown in Figure 1. Concerning CAS process (Figure 1a), biodegradability increases going from the bottom left corner to the top right corner and with larger bubble diameters. As for quaternary treatments (Figure 1b), micropollutants reactivity with ozone increases with K_{O3} , while affinity with activated carbon increases with K_{OW} ; bubble diameter reflects the pK_a : micropollutants with pK_a values far from neutral exhibits greater variability in adsorption efficiency. Combining micropollutants positions in Figure 1b with bubble color, representing biodegradability derived by Figure 1a (darker the color, higher the biodegradability), it is possible to have a preliminary indication of the potential removal in WWTPs in view of the application of the UWWTD.

A total of 52 articles were collected, providing data on 89 WWTPs from different parts of the world, with data from 49 WWTPs located in European Union and directly interested in the UWWTD. 65 provided influent concentration values, while 37 provided concentrations at both the inlet and outlet of quaternary treatments. The removal efficiency of each micropollutant was calculated and reported in Figure 2, both for the biological treatment, the quaternary treatments, and the overall WWTP when quaternary treatments were present.

No micropollutants achieve the 80% removal in the CAS process, with the highest median removals for IRB, BTR and CLR, and the lowest ones for CND, CBZ and AMS, highlighting the need of quaternary treatments. When the WWTPs include quaternary treatments, all micropollutants achieve a median removal efficiency above 80%, satisfying the UWWTD requirements. Looking at the quaternary treatments only, most of them reach the 80% median removal, except for BTR, IRB, 5MBT and CND, being among the micropollutants displaying the lowest affinity towards ozonation (Figure 1b).

Figure 1. Suitability maps for (a) CAS process and (b) quaternary treatments (ozonation and activated carbon adsorption). The color of the micropollutants' label indicates their belonging to Category 1 (black) and Category 2 (grey) of the UWWTD.

Figure 2. Micropollutants removal in CAS process, in quaternary treatments, and in the WWTP where quaternary treatments are in place. The colour of the micropollutants' label indicates their belonging to Category 1 (black) and Category 2 (grey) of the UWWTD. The green dotted line represents the 80% removal targeted by the UWWTD.

Economic and environmental impact analysis

The choice of quaternary treatment technology depends on factors like energy consumption, operational complexity, the type of micropollutants to be removed, and treatment goals. Ozonation requires high energy, while activated carbon adsorption is simpler but may involve frequent regeneration. Activated carbon ensure complete pollutant removal, while ozonation may need additional steps to manage residual toxicity. All these factors determine the economic and environmental impact of each treatment option.

Concerning the costs related to the implementation of the quaternary treatments, the performed cost analysis highlighted that the higher economic impacts are related to: (i) ozone concentration in the contact reactor, (ii) regeneration frequency of GAC, (iii) dosage and disposal of PAC. To account for the variability of costs related to these factors, a sensitivity analysis on the cost estimation was performed by varying them in realistic conditions; results are shown in Figure 3. The per-capita cost does not significantly change as a function of WWTP capacity, with notable differences only between 10,000 and 100,000 PE, as observed by Pistocchi et al. (2022). PAC adsorption seems to be the most expensive solution. However, changes in operating parameters substantially impact the costs, possibly affecting the ranking of the three process options.

As for the environmental impact assessment, the risk associated to the micropollutants present in the wastewater in the various treatment steps has been estimated. Some micropollutants (4,5-MBT, AMS, CTL, HDC and MTP) have RQ values below 0.1, even at influent concentrations, meaning they do not require specific treatments. Even if quaternary treatments are considered, the residual effluent concentrations of VEN, DCF, BTR and CBZ imply an intermediate risk (RQ 0.1-10), while a high risk (RQ>10) is posed by CND and IRB. These findings stress that, although WWTPs with quaternary treatments achieve the 80% removal target of the UWWTD, it does not ensure the absence of a residual environmental risk for several micropollutants.

Figure 3. Yearly per-capita cost for each investigated quaternary treatment, at different WWTP capacity, depending on selected process parameters: (a) ozone concentration in the contact tank; (b) time between two regenerations of GAC; (c) dosage of PAC and waste sludge (not recirculated) sent to incineration with respect to the generated sludge.

CONCLUSIONS

This review provides support in the application of the UWWTD, by offering a comprehensive knowledge on micropollutants removal in wastewater. Our results highlight the need of quaternary treatments to achieve the required 80% removal efficiency, even though this does not guarantee the absence of environmental risk. Therefore, an integrated approach to manage micropollutants is essential, with strategies aimed at source reduction for the more toxic substances. As for the associated costs, the yearly per-capita costs of quaternary treatments proved to be more influenced by the selected operating parameters values rather than by the WWTP capacity.

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